

Merocyanines Derived from Thiazolo [3, 2-a] Benzimidazol-3(2H)-One

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Several merocyanines (I; $n = 1, 2$) from thiazolo [3, 2-a] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one have been synthesised by condensing its acetanilido methylene and acetanilido allylidene intermediates with different 2-methyl quaternary salts. The relative basicities of the various 2-methyl heterocyclic compounds have been evaluated from the $C = O$ absorption frequency of merocyanines. This order has also been confirmed from Brooker's Deviation factor¹.

CARBOCYANINES (merocyanines) from different types of ketomethylene compounds are well known²⁻³. The study of the literature revealed that the bridge head nitrogen containing heterocyclic ketomethylene compounds have not been used for the synthesis of the dyes. Hence it was considered of interest to synthesise different types of merocyanines from thiazolo [3, 2-a] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one, which possesses a $-CH_2-CO-$ system. This compound was prepared from 2-mercapto benzimidazole with mono-chloro acetic acid subsequent cyclisation of the thiol acetic acid according to Pujari *et al.*⁴ The thiazolo benzimidazole compound furnished acetanilido methylene and acetanilido allylidene intermediates with diphenyl forma-

I ; $n = 1$, and 2

The intermediates were condensed with various 2-methyl quaternary salts in alcohol and triethylamine to get the dicarbo ($n = 1$) and tetracarbo ($n = 2$) cyanines.

In evaluating the relative basicities of various 2-methyl heterocyclic compounds, used in the dye synthesis, the carbonyl group absorption bands in IR spectra were taken into consideration. The IR spectrum of the ketomethylene compound shows $C = O$ absorption band at 1740 cm^{-1} , but a bathochromic shift occurred, when it was linked up with the heterocyclic moiety by means of methin groups. The greater the basicity of the heterocyclic ring (nucleus B; I) the greater will be the delocalisation of $C = O$ in the acidic nucleus which will result in more bathochromic shift. The absorption band for the carbonyl group in dimethin merocyanine derived from benzimidazole and lepidine appeared at 1660 cm^{-1} , whereas the carbonyl absorption of the dimethin merocyanine derived from benzimidazole and benzothiazole appeared at 1700 cm^{-1} (Table 1). Since the former absorbs at a higher wavelength than the latter, lepidine will be more basic than benzothiazole.

midine and beta-anilino acrolein anil dihydro-chloride respectively in the medium of acetic anhydride.

The same pattern was also noticed in the carbonyl absorption of the tetramethin merocyanines (Table 1). Therefore the relative decreasing basicity will follow

TABLE I

B	n	Carbonyl absorption	λ_{max} methin oxonols	λ_{max} methin cyanines	Calc. λ_{max}	Obs. λ_{max}	Deviation
Benzothiazolyl-2	1	1700	480	560	520	515	5
-Do-	2	1680	570	650	610	600	10
4-Phenyl thiazolyl-2	1	1675	480	560	520	518	2
-Do-	2	1670	570	650	610	600	10
Quinolyl-2	1	1670	480	610	545	545	0
-Do-	2	1665	570	700	635	620	15
Quinolyl-4	1	1660	480	710	595	600	6
-Do-	2	1655	570	800	685	680	5

the following sequence :—Quinoline-4 > Quinoline-2 > 4-phenyl thiazole > Benzothiazole. This order of basicity has also been observed by considering the deviation in absorption maxima, which were calculated by subtracting the absorption maxima value of the merocyanines from the mean value of methin cyanines and oxonols. Since according to Brooker, "the greater the deviation the greater will be the basicity for a series of merocyanines derived from a fixed acidic nucleus" the relative order of decreasing basicities will follow the above sequence (Table 1).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The IR spectra of the compounds were taken in Perkin Elmer 257 grating spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian 100 MHz spectrophotometer in DMSO-*d*⁶ using TMS as internal reference. The chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS.

2-Mercapto benzimidazole : It was prepared from *o*-phenylene diamine and potassium ethyl xanthate following the method of Van Allan⁵.

2-Benzimidazolthiol acetic acid : It was obtained as white crystalline solid in 85% yield from 2-mercapto benzimidazole and mono chloro acetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. Recrystallisation from alcohol gave m.p. 210°. (lit⁶ m.p. 215).

Thiazolo [3, 2-*a*] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one : The above thiol acetic acid (2.8 g) was treated with a mixture of acetic anhydride (10 ml) and pyridine (15 ml) and heated on a steam bath for 5 hrs. On cooling shining crystals separated which were filtered and finally crystallised from ethanol using norite, as white needles. Yield-65%, M.P. 178° (lit⁶ m.p. 180°). (Found : C; 56.75, H; 3.47, N; 14.41, C₉H₈N₂SO requires C; 56.84, H; 3.15, N; 14.73), λ_{max} in nujol (cm⁻¹); 1375 (CH₂ symmetrical deformation), 1450 (CH₂ deformation), 1510 (CN stretching), 1615 (C = N), 1740 (C = O), δ ; 4.5 (S), 7.5 (m).

2-Acetanilidomethylene thiazolo[3, 2-*a*] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one : A mixture of the above keto methylene compound (1.9 g) and diphenyl formamidine (1.9 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (20 ml) for 30 min. After cooling the solution was poured into cold

water, which furnished one yellow precipitate. This was dried and crystallised from alcohol. Yield : 55%, M.P. 195°. (Found : C; 64.28, H; 3.62, N; 12.46, C₁₈H₁₃N₃SO₂; requires C; 64.47, H; 3.88, N; 12.53).

2-Acetanilido allylidene thiazolo [3, 2-*a*] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one : A mixture of the keto methylene compound (1.9 g) and beta-anilino acrolein anil dihydrochloride (3.0 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride for 1 hr and the compound was isolated as above intermediate. Yield-50%, M.P. 216°. (Found : C; 66.32, H; 3.86, N; 11.21; C₂₀H₁₅N₃SO₂ requires C; 66.47, H; 4.16, N; 11.63).

2-(3-Methyl 4-phenyl thiazolin-2-ylidene-ethylidene) thiazolo [3, 2-*a*] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one : A solution of acetanilido methylene intermediate (0.36 g) and 2-methyl 4-phenyl thiazole methiodide (0.32 g) in absolute alcohol was refluxed with 2 drops of triethylamine for 10 min. After cooling yellow needles separated, which were crystallised from alcohol. Yield—75%, M.P. 225°. (Found : C; 64.53, H; 3.56, N; 10.54; C₂₁H₁₅N₃S₂O requires C; 64.77, H; 3.85, N; 10.78) λ_{max} in nujol² (cm⁻¹); 1490 (CN stretching), 1590 (C = N), 1675 (C = O), λ_{max} 518 m μ in ethanol, log ϵ ; 4.8190. δ ; 6.9 and 7.3 (d, J; 12 cps indicating trans orientation, 4.0 (S, > N—CH₃), 7.6(m, aromatic protons).

2-(3-Methyl benzothiazolin 2-ylidene-ethylidene) thiazolo [3, 2-*a*] benzimidazol-3(2H)-one : It was prepared as above from acetanilido methylene intermediate and 2-methyl benzothiazole methiodide in 60% yield. M.P. > 250° (Found : C; 62.49, H; 3.25, N; 11.48; C₁₈H₁₃N₃S₂O requires C; 62.80, H; 3.58, N; 11.56), ν_{max} (cm⁻¹); 1485(CN-stretching), 1660 (C = N), 1700 (C = O), λ_{max} 515 m μ in ethanol, log ϵ ; 4.7218. δ ; 6.8 and 7.1 (d, 2H), 3.5 (S, > N—CH₃), 7.5 (m, aromatic protons).

The physical and analytical data of the various dyes prepared have been recorded in Table 2.

Bis-[thiazolo (3, 2-*a*) benzimidazol-3(2H)-one] methin oxonol : Benzimidazol-3(2H)-one (0.4 g) and ethyl-orthoformate (0.5 g) were boiled for 10 min in acetic anhydride (5 ml) in the presence of triethylamine. The desired product separated on acidification with HCl. Yield—65%, M.P. 2150°, λ_{max} 480 m μ in ethanol.

TABLE 2

B	n	M.P. °C	λ_{max}	log ϵ	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		% Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
4-Phenylthiazolyl	2	> 250	600	4.3210	66.17	66.50	4.21	4.09	10.06	10.12
Benzothiazolyl-2	2	> 250	600	4.4531	—	—	—	—	—	—
Quinolyl-2	1	> 250	545	4.3652	70.46	70.58	4.12	4.20	11.53	11.76
-Do-	2	245	620	4.4573	—	—	—	—	—	—
Quinolyl-4	1	> 250	600	4.6512	70.34	70.58	4.14	4.20	11.48	11.76
-Do-	2	> 250	680	4.6434	—	—	—	—	—	—

Yield varies from 40-60%.

The trimethin oxonol was prepared from the ketomethylene compound and 1, 3, 3-trimethoxy propene M.P. > 250°, λ_{max} 570 m μ in alcohol.

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